

ADT36, WP, IR20, and Jaya showed lower values under saline conditions. This means that under stress conditions, chlorophyll content was affected to a greater extent in susceptible varieties than in tolerant varieties. Hybrids IR20/CO 43, ADT 36/CO 43, WP/CSR10, and IR20/CSR10, however, per-

formed better under saline conditions than under normal conditions.

All hybrids were generally found to be more tolerant compared with their more susceptible parents (Table 2). This suggests that salt tolerance is a dominant trait. It is possible to incorporate salt tolerance through hybridization between tol-

erant and susceptible parents. Increased salt tolerance in hybrids is a consequence of increased seedling vigor.

Reference

Koleyoreas SA. 1958. A new method for determining drought resistance. *Plant Physiol.* 33:22.

Exogenous glycinebetaine reduces sodium accumulation in salt-stressed rice plants

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Glycinebetaine (GB) is a compatible organic solute produced by several plant species to cope with salt or water stress. This compound is involved in osmotic adjustment as well as in protecting several cellular structures. It is well established that rice is unable to synthesize this compound because it lacks choline monoxygenase (CMO), which is involved in the synthesis of betaine aldehyde, the immediate precursor of GB. It has also been reported that exogenous GB protects rice from salt stress by maintaining photosystem II integrity and relative water content (Harinasut et al 1996). Its effect on sodium nutrition in salt-stressed rice, however, was never reported.

In a phytotron experiment, a salt-sensitive rice cultivar—I Kong Pao—maintained on nutrient solution (Yoshida et al 1976; renewed each week) was subjected to various NaCl doses (0, 30, 50, and 100 mM), with or without simultaneous exposure to 1 mM GB (Sigma Chemical). Plants were exposed to salt stress at the seedling stage (20 d old; 100 plants per treatment) on 25-L tanks in a complete randomized block. Ten surviving plants were collected each week during a subsequent 1-mo experiment. Relative growth rate was quantified on a dry-weight basis and ion concentration was determined after digestion of organic matter with nitric acid by an in-

ductively coupled argon plasma emission spectrophotometer.

The presence of GB in nutrient solution had no deleterious effect on unstressed plants, but it clearly improved surviving plant percentages and growing abilities of salt-treated ones (see table). At the highest NaCl dose (100 mM), exogenous GB affords protection only during the 2 wk of exposure to salinity. The positive effect of exogenous GB was associated with reduced sodium accumulation and with the maintenance of potassium concentration in all parts of salinized plants as shown in the figure for plants exposed to various NaCl doses during 2 wk. Exog-

Surviving percentages* (S%) and relative growth rates (RGR, expressed on a dry-weight basis in $g\ g^{-1}\ d^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$) of plants of salt-sensitive cultivar I Kong Pao exposed during 4 wk to various NaCl doses (0, 30, 50, and 100 mM) on nutrient solution in the presence (+) or absence (-) of 1 mM GB.

Parameter	Duration of exposure (wk)	0 mM		30 mM		50 mM		100 mM	
		-GB	+GB	-GB	+GB	-GB	+GB	-GB	+GB
S%	1	100 a	100 a	100 a	100 a	71 c	85 b	72 c	83 b
	2	100 a	99 a	83 b	86 b	70 c	87 b	51 d	78 b
	3	98 a	100 a	71 c	86 b	54 d	73 c	32 e	45 e
	4	100 a	100 a	65 c	75 c	38 e	62 d	7 f	12 f
Shoot RGR (in $g\ g^{-1}\ d^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)	1	113.4 a	108.9 a	85.2 b	100.7 a	55.5 c	71.6 b	49.0 c	58.3 c
	2	98.8 a	102.4 a	77.7 b	97.1 a	17.5 e	35.2 c	15.6 e	29.6 d
	3	95.1 a	86.4 b	50.2 c	81.9 b	*	22.3 d	*	*
	4	77.5 b	80.3 b	38.2 c	69.3 c	*	28.9 d	*	*
Root RGR (in $g\ g^{-1}\ d^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)	1	86.0 a	83.7 a	80.1 a	75.4 a	44.4 d	58.6 c	40.3 d	53.8 c
	2	77.9 a	80.8 a	63.9 b	71.3 b	39.7 d	55.7 c	11.6 f	38.4 d
	3	68.9 b	71.2 b	65.5 b	66.2 b	10.4 f	21.6 e	*	22.8 e
	4	72.3 b	68.6 b	49.7 c	68.5 b	*	12.6 f	*	*

Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ (χ^2 test); * = not significantly different from 0.

enous GB had no effect on calcium and magnesium nutrition of stressed plants, whatever the NaCl dose (detailed data not shown). These results suggest that GB may have a positive impact on both absorption and translocation of monovalent cations in salt-stressed rice and that its synthesis by transferring gene coding for CMO may constitute an interesting goal for genetic engineering in this species.

References

- Harinasut P, Tsutsui K, Takebe T, Nomura M, Takebe T, Kishitani S. 1996. Exogenous glycinebetaine accumulation and increased salt-tolerance in rice seedlings. *Biosci. Biotechnol. Biochem.* 60:366–368.
- Yoshida S, Forno OA, Cock JH, Gomez KA. 1976. *Laboratory manual for physiological studies of rice.* Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute.

Sodium and potassium concentrations in roots and shoots of rice plants (cv I Kong Pao) exposed during 2 wk to a nutrient solution containing various NaCl doses (0, 30, 50, and 100 mM) in the presence (+) or absence (-) of 1 mM GB. Each value is the mean of at least four replicates and vertical bars are S.E.

Instructional videos available

The Leaf Color Chart (LCC) (8:20 min)

Farmers generally observe the color of rice leaves to determine a rice crop's need for nitrogen fertilizer. Dark green rice leaves mean a high nitrogen content, while pale green rice leaves necessitate the application of more nitrogen fertilizer.

Mere observation, however, holds no absolute guarantee of measurement accuracy. Thus, to better help farmers determine their rice crops' need for nitrogen, the leaf color chart (LCC) was developed.

The *Leaf Color Chart (LCC)* instructional video was produced to familiarize farmers and extension workers with the proper use of this new and affordable farming implement.

Portable Chlorophyll Meter for Nitrogen Management in Rice (13:30 min)

In agriculture, excess nitrates can actually be highly damaging to crops and the environment. There is thus a need to efficiently manage the application of nitrogen fertilizers on rice crops.

The *Portable Chlorophyll Meter for Nitrogen Management in Rice* introduces the features and use of the chlorophyll or SPAD meter, which is capable of measuring the relative nitrogen content in plant leaves through a simple, quick, and nondestructive procedure.

Go breAk inTo the Code (13:30 min)

Genetic engineering need not be a property of the scientific few. This is what IRRI had in mind when it produced *Go breAk inTo the Code*: to make the general public grasp and understand the seemingly complicated science through a visually stunning, fast-paced, and entertaining presentation of the genetic code, DNA sequencing, and plant biotechnology.

The video also gives the public a glimpse as to how IRRI scientists are redesigning the rice plant—that most important food staple—using biotechnology tools.

These instructional videos are available in English, in the 3/4-inch u-matic and VHS formats, and in the NTSC, SECAM, or PAL systems.

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